

Impact of Paired-Problem-Solving Strategy on Performance in Concept Evolution among Secondary School Divergent Learners in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of paired-problem-solving strategy on performance in concept evolution among secondary school divergent biology learners in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State. Two research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the research. Quasi experimental research Design was used for the study. The experimental group was taught concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy while the control group were exposed to Conventional lecture method. Population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two biology students in Gusau Metropolis during the 2023/2024 academic session in Gusau, Zamfara State. A sample size of 154 (Male, 82 and Female, 72) students were selected from the target population using multistage sampling technique. The validated Students' Evolution Performance Test (SEPT) with reliability coefficients of 0.76, was used for data collection. Data collected was analysed using SPSS version 26.0 at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. Mean, mean difference, and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions and t-test Statistic was used to test the hypotheses at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. Results revealed that significant difference exists between the academic performance of divergent learners exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy and those taught using Conventional lecture method and likewise academic performance of divergent male and female learners exposed to Paired-problem solving strategy. The findings revealed that Paired-problem-solving strategy enhanced divergent learners' academic performance. It is thus recommended that, all secondary school biology teachers should be encouraged to use modern teaching method such as the Paired-problem-solving strategy through training and retraining programs.

Keywords: Paired-problem-solving, Concept of Evolution, Divergent Biology Learners

Introduction

The science teachers' role in fostering students' active involvement in doing and learning of science, is seen as crucial for students' achievement in science. Otuka (2016), described science as a dynamic field of human endeavour, and that the development of any country depends largely on the teaching and learning of science. Thus, a country's educational policies and programs are directed toward science of which biology is an important branch. The economic strength of a nation is always assessed in terms of its performance in science and technology.

Teaching evolution at secondary school level requires the use of effective teaching strategy in order to make students understand the concept. Many strategies that involve active participation of students in the learning process (student-centered) that is concept mapping strategy, laboratory method, problem-based strategy among others. Despite the significant contribution of these to learn within themselves (in pairs) without much interference of other learners. Strategies in learning science concepts, the use of Paired-problem-solving-strategy gives learners a chance.

Paired-problems-solving strategy is one of the effective teaching strategy teachers used in teaching. In this regard Narode (2012), described Paired-Problem-Solving Strategy as a teaching procedure developed by Lohead and Whimbey in 1987 in order to promote students' ability to solve problems by the use of verbal descriptions. These

descriptions could be through proving and clarifying questions, in pairs each student takes roles, one will serve as a problem solver while the other student serves as a listener. The student designated as the problem solver begins by reading the problem aloud to the other student (the listener) and verbalizes all thoughts on how to solve the problem. The problem solver does all the talking and all the writing about the problem. The problem solver is responsible for articulating all ideas as they occur, whereas the listener has an opposite task. This shows that, whenever the problem solver is talking, the listener must suspend solving the problem so that complete concentration and attention is devoted toward understanding the problem solver's solution. Through Paired-problem-solving strategy, students articulate ideas thereby improving their performance, which could motivate the convergent and divergent students.

Until the end of 18th century, the application of Paired-problem-solving strategy was decreased. Robins (2011), suggests that "students routinely make vast improvement in their year over year academic performance after the Paired-problem solving strategy is introduced. Academic performance of students is the centre around which the whole education system revolves. The success and failure of any educational institution is measure in terms of academic performance of students. Arshad, Zaidi and Mahmood (2015) indicated that academic performance measures education outcome. They stressed that it shows and measures the extent to which an educational institution, teachers and students have achieved their educational goals.

Yusuf, Onifade and Bello (2016) added that it consists of scores obtained by students in an assessment such as class exercise, mock examination and end of semester examination. The definition given by authors shows that the definition of academic performance is based on measurable outcomes such as class exercise, test and examinations results. Based on this the operational definition used in this study is the results obtained by students at post-test. This study therefore found out the impact of Paired-problem-solving strategy on performance in evolution concepts among secondary school students of different learning styles (convergent/divergent) in Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Learning style is another variable in this study. Many learning styles experts according to Gilakjani (2014) showed the theory that students will learn more and will enjoy the class experience and environment when they can use their preferred learning styles. To address this concern, teachers should understand their students' learning styles preferences and be interesting in developing teaching approaches to address the learning needs of all their students, because Ibe (2013) explained, that good teaching approach or method will help make the class session more effective and encourage students' participation in the class. Ibe (2013), further defined learning styles as the ways individuals prepare to absorb and incorporate new information. Different people have different ways of learning, and that those ways are neither good nor bad given various preferences for perceiving and processing information. The study of individual differences was important in science teaching, because it revealed the mental resources involved in learning specific domains and could relate them to persistent students' difficulties. Stamovlasis, Kypraios and Papageorgiou (2015) ascertained that convergence and divergence are two distinct cognitive styles, rather than opposites, that are introduced as special aspects of intelligence. Convergence is the ability of an individual to focus on the one right answer in order to find the solution of a problem, whereas divergence is one's ability to respond flexibly and successfully to problems requiring the generation of several solutions. Divergent thinking is usually correlated with creativity and convergence is associated with intelligence. Nwangbo and Aham (2015) observed that the populations of students in a class in most cases are made up of varying intellectuals and learning styles which to a large extent has effect on academic performance. In line with this, Shuaibu, Lawal and Bichi (2015), highlighted common cognitive styles capable of affecting students' attitude and performance to include: field dependence and field independence, reflective and impulsive, convergent and divergent. Shuaibu (2017) posited that the classroom environment consists of students with different learning abilities and psychological construct, some are extroverts, some are introverts, some are independent personality, while others are of dependent personality among others. In addition, students thinking and information processing significantly differ, which have direct impact on their academic performance in various subjects. There are various documented cognitive styles that influence students' academic performance, also according to Shuaibu (2017) these includes visual and haptic, visualized and verbalized, field dependent and field independent, holists and serialist and convergent and divergent. Kolb (1999), has suggested four different learning styles: Accommodator, Divergent, Assimilators and Convergent. Divergent students were used for the study in order to find out whether the paired-problem-solving strategy enhance divergent students' academic performance.

According to Dantani (2011), in most countries of the world the educational provision for boys and girls was clearly differentiated. Gender according to Bichi (2015), is the amount of masculinity and femininity found in a person

and obviously there are mixture of both in a few human beings, the normal male has the prepondence of masculinity and a normal female has femininity. Various studies have been carried out in science education to ascertain the influence of gender with regards to academic performance. However, Okeke (2018), explained that female students were significantly better than their male counterparts and that there was a significant difference between male and female students in their ability to solve quantitative problems. Suleiman et al (2019), narrated that, to which a society placed values, some societies regarded males to be the champion of activities and events happening around the environment. Moreover, Gor, Othuon and Migunde (2020), asserted that, studies in Nigeria have however, revealed mixed reports on gender difference in science performance. Some researchers have provided reports that there are no longer distinguishing differences in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor skill achievements of students in respect of gender. Furthermore, Dawal (2021), revealed that there is a gender differences in the attitude and achievement of students towards science. Male students exhibited positive attitude towards physics, chemistry and mathematics than their female counterparts while the female students have positive attitude towards biology.

Gender bias in science classrooms has been and still continues to be a problem. Meanwhile the contradictive evidences in academic performance due to gender necessitate the need to verify how Paired-problem-solving strategy can affect biology student's performance in respect to gender. Therefore, this study used Paired-problem-solving strategy in teaching evolution concepts to secondary school biology students in order to see whether or not it has impact in the learning styles of divergent learners. Sulaiman (2023) investigated the effects of Contextual approach on confidence and performance in electrochemistry among divergent and convergent secondary school students in Bauchi State, Nigeria and found out that the divergent and convergent students in the experimental group performed better than the divergent and convergent students in the control group. The study carried out by Sulaiman (2023), is similar to the present study in terms of academic performance, learning style, research design, school, alpha level of 0.05 and procedure for data analysis but differs in terms of motivation, sample, population, instrument, r-value, subject and location.

Adigun, Aghiomesi and John (2015) investigated the effect of gender on students' academic performance in computer studies in secondary schools in new Bussa, Borgu local government of Niger State, Nigeria. The result of the study showed that even though the male students had slightly better performance compared to the female students, it was not significant. This better performance was found to be pronounced in the private schools which was shown to possess the best male brains found in the study area. The study carried out by Adigun, Aghiomesi and John (2015), is similar to the present study in terms of academic performance, gender, statistical tool and p value of 0.05 level of significance but differs in terms of teaching strategy, motivation, learning styles, r-value, location, sample and population.

Goni, Yanagawali, Ali. and Bularafa (2015) examined the gender differences in students' academic performance in collage of education in Borno State, Nigeria. The result indicated that there were no significant differences exist between gender and academic performance in collage of education in Borno State. The study carried out by Goni, Yanagawali, Ali. and Bularafa (2015), is similar to the present study in terms of teaching strategy, academic performance, gender, research design but differs in terms of teaching strategy, motivation, learning styles, location, sample, population and r-value.

This study therefore investigated the impact of paired-problem-solving strategy on performance in concept evolution among secondary school divergent biology learners in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State and the study also took gender into cognizance.

Biology is one of the natural sciences offered by secondary school students in Nigeria and the most popular science subject students registered during their West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE). Ibe (2012), blame performance of biology students in external examination on biology teachers' insensitivity to the nature of biology when planning instructional activities in the classroom. Ibe (2012), further stressed that biology is not one of the subjects that can be mastered by mere memorization of the basic rules. It requires total determination, sound theoretical knowledge and intensive practice in application. In line with this Manalanga and Awelani (2014), identified possible factors responsible for the poor performance in biology amongst other factors to include; method of teaching, lack of well stocked libraries and lack of laboratories and biology textbooks. Achor, Ogbeba and Umoru (2014) pointed out that, it is worthwhile to note that despite the importance and the popularity of biology compared to other science subjects, students' performance in biology in both internal and external examinations have remained poor over the years. Therefore, teaching and learning of biology at all levels of education require teachers to use effective

strategies in order to facilitate learning and consider their learning styles. There are several techniques a teacher can use to make his/her teaching become more effective.

Objectives of the Study

1. Determine the impact of Paired-problem-solving strategy and conventional lecture teaching method on the academic performance of divergent biology learners in Concept evolution
2. determine the impact of Paired-problem-solving strategy on the academic performance in concept evolution among divergent male and female biology learners?

Research Questions

The following questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent biology learners taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy and those exposed to conventional lecture teaching method?
2. What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent male and female biology learners taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent biology learners when taught concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy and those exposed to Conventional lecture teaching method.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female divergent learners when taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy.

Methodology

Pretest and posttest quasi experimental-control group design as proposed by Sambo (2005) involving two groups randomly divided into experimental group (EG) and control group (CG) consisting intact class of S.S.2 students was used for the study. The two groups were pretested (O_1) to determine the group equivalence based on the ability of the students and post-tested (O_2) to check determine their academic performance (AP) among divergent students (DV). The experimental groups were taught evolution concepts using paired-problem solving strategy (X_1) while the control group students were taught the same concepts using Conventional lecture method (X_0).

Population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two biology students in Gusau Metropolis during the 2023/2024 academic session in Gusau, Zamfara State. A sample size of 154 (Male, 82 and Female, 72) students were selected from the target population using multistage sampling technique. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select eight (8), secondary schools based on location. Four (4) male and (4) four female schools. The reason for the stratification was to ensure that both male and female schools were involved in the sample. The S.S. II students of all the eight schools (8) were given a test in order to find out if there is any ability difference in their academic performance, The test questions were from Zamfara State 2021 screening examination questions on Biology for S.S.II students and their scores were subjected to One-Way Analysis of Variance at Alpha = 0.05 level of significance. After running the test, significant difference was found among the schools at $\alpha = 0.000$ which is less than 0.05 level of significance. In order to find out the schools that are similar, Scheffe's Post Hoc test of multiple comparison was carried out and four schools were found to be significant namely; Schools D, E, F and G. A total no. of 348 students comprising all the S.S II students of four sampled schools were used as the study sample which is viable for the study and is in line with the Central Limit Theorem. Tuckman (1975) and Sambo (2008), recommended that a sample size with minimum of 30 students is viable for an experimental study. Convergent and divergent students were identified based on their scores from the students' learning style inventory (SELSI) which was given to them as an instrument, the instrument contained eight (8) items and students were asked to write five (5) uses of each item, each correct answer attracts 1 mark. The test items were scored over forty (40) and was used for categorizing the students into the two learning styles (i.e. convergent and divergent) Suleiman (2023) stated that students' score between 0-19 marks was taken for convergers and scores between 20-40 marks was taken for divergers. Divergent students were used for the study.

The Students' Evolution Performance Test (SEPT) was adapted from past questions of West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council Organization (NECO) of (2014-2021) based on Bloom's Taxonomy. A multiple choice of 60 questions with options A-D consisting one correct answer and three distractors for each item was used. To ensure face, construct and content validity of the instruments, the Students' Evolution Performance Test (SEPT) was validated by experts from the department of Science Education. test-retest method was used to statistically estimate the internal consistency of the instrument. This is in line with Sambo (2008) who recommends two weeks for test-retest procedure. The score for the instruments was correlated using Pearson-Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) statistic and the reliability coefficient was found to be 0.76 indicating a strong positive relationship and therefore consider to be reliable for the study to measure the academic performance of the study subjects. Maduabum (2004) stated that any reliability coefficient of 0.5 and above is good enough for good instant decision to be taken.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent biology learners taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy and those exposed to conventional lecture teaching method? Means and standard deviations were computed as contained in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Post-test Scores of Divergent Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	Decision
Academic Performance	Divergent (Experimental)	74	42.74	9.76	13.77	Difference exists
	Divergent (Control Group)	80	28.97	9.69		

Table 1 showed that there was difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent students in the experimental and control groups. The mean scores of 42.74 and standard deviation of 9.76 for divergent students in the experimental group is higher than the mean score of 28.97 and the standard deviation of 9.69 for divergent students in the control group. The mean difference of 13.77 showed that divergent students taught evolution concept using Paired-problem-solving strategy with a mean of 41.74 performed better than divergent students in the control group who had a mean score of 28.97.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent male and female biology learners taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy?

To answer this research question, the posttest scores of divergent male and female learners exposed to paired-problem-solving teaching strategy were subjected to descriptive statistics. Means and standard deviation were computed and used to draw Table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Post-test Scores of Divergent Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	Decision
Academic Performance	Divergent (Male)	34	44.06	8.43	17.13	Difference Exists
	Divergent (Female)	40	26.93	6.06		

Table 2 showed that there was difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent male and female students in the experimental group. The mean scores of 44.06 and standard deviation of 8.43 for divergent male students in the experimental group is higher than the mean score of 26.93 and the standard deviation of 6.06 for divergent female students in the experimental group. The mean difference of 17.13 showed that divergent male students taught evolution concept using Paired-problem-solving strategy with a mean of 44.06 performed better than divergent female students in the experimental group who had a mean score of 26.93. To find out if the mean difference is significant or not, the data was further subjected to an independent samples t-test at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent biology learners when taught concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy and those exposed to Conventional lecture teaching method.

To test null hypothesis one, the post-test scores obtained from SEPT for the divergent learners in the experimental and control groups were subjected to an independent sample t-test statistic at $\alpha = 0.05$. Summary of the analysis is presented in Table 2.

Table 3: Independent t-test Analysis of Mean Performance Scores between Divergent Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	t	P	Remark	Decision
Divergent (Experimental)	74	42.74	9.76	152	8.90	0.000	Significant	Ho ₁ Rejected
Divergent (Control Group)	80	28.79	9.69					

$\alpha = 0.05$

Results of the independent samples t-test statistic in Table 3 revealed that significant difference exists between the academic performance of divergent students exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy and those taught using Conventional lecture method. Reason being that calculated p value of 0.000 is less than the alpha level of 0.05. The computed Mean academic performances are 42.74 and 28.79 by divergent students exposed to Paired-problem solving strategy and those taught using Conventional lecture method indicating a mean academic performance difference of 13.77 in favour of the divergent students exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy. Consequently, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the academic performance scores of divergent students when taught evolution concepts using Paired-problem-solving strategy and those exposed to Conventional lecture method, is hereby rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female divergent learners when taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy.

The post-test scores of male and female divergent learners exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy were subjected to an independent samples t-test at $\alpha = 0.05$ and presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Independent t-test Analysis of Mean Performance Scores Between Divergent Students in the Experimental Group

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	t	p	Remark	Decision
Divergent (Male)	34	44.06	8.43	72	10.14	0.000	Significant	Ho ₂ Rejected
Divergent (Female)	40	26.93	6.06					

$\alpha = 0.05$

Results of the independent samples t-test statistic in Table 4 revealed that significant difference exists between the academic performance of divergent male and female students exposed to Paired-problem solving strategy. Reason being that calculated p value of 0.000 is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Their computed Mean academic performances are 44.06 and 26.93 for divergent male and female students exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy indicating a mean academic performance difference of 17.13 in favour of the divergent male students exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy. Consequently, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the academic performance scores of male and female divergent students when taught evolution concepts using Paired-problem-solving strategy, is hereby rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This study investigated the impact of paired-problem-solving strategy on performance in concept evolution among secondary school divergent biology learners in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State. Divergent students were

categorized into the experimental and control groups. Divergent students in experimental group were taught evolution concept in biology using paired-problem solving strategy while divergent students in control group were taught the same concepts using lecture method. The data of this study were based on performance of divergent students obtained from Students' Evolution Performance Test (SEPT) and their performance according to the variable being measured were analysed according to research hypotheses developed for the study.

The findings of this study in Table 1 and 3 showed that divergent learners taught concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy performed significantly better than divergent learners taught same concepts using Conventional lecture method. The result shows a significant difference in the mean scores of convergent learners exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy and those taught using Conventional lecture method. The substantial change in performance is in favour of the divergent learners in the experimental group which suggested a greater effectiveness of Paired-problem-solving strategy over the Conventional lecture method of teaching. This finding is in line with that of Sulaiman (2023) who found out that the divergent and convergent students in the experimental group performed better than the divergent and convergent students in the control group. This finding gains further support from Hajesfandiari, Mehrdad and Karimi (2014) who opined that divergent thinking is mostly based on creativity and used in open-ended problems that creativity is a fundamental part.

The result from answering research question two and testing hypothesis two in Table 2 and 4 showed that significant difference exists between the mean academic performance of male and female divergent learners taught concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy. This indicates that divergent male learners performed better than divergent female learners when exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy. The use of Paired-problem-solving strategy in teaching concept evolution taking gender of divergent students into consideration showed that Paired-problem-solving strategy favour one gender over the other. Thus, the use of Paired-problem-solving strategy is not gender friendly as male divergent learner's performance were enhanced more than that of female divergent learners after the treatment. This finding supports that of Adigun, Aghiomesi and John (2015) who reported male students had slightly better performance compared to the female students, the difference was not significant. The finding disagrees with that of Goni, Yanagawali, Ali and Bularafa (2015) who found out that there was no significant difference between gender and academic performance after exposure to treatment.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from this study, it was concluded that Paired-problem solving strategy is an effective strategy in teaching divergent biology secondary school learners as it helped improve divergent learners' academic performance among secondary school students in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State and Paired-problem solving strategy improves divergent male learners' academic performance.

Recommendations

In this study the following recommendations were made in line with the findings;

1. It was discovered that paired-problem-solving strategy enhances divergent learner's academic performance. All secondary school biology teachers should be encouraged and motivated to use modern teaching method such as the Paired-problem-solving strategy by training and retraining through sponsorship to workshops, seminars and in house trainings.
2. Paired-problem-solving strategy was found to improve divergent male learners' academic performance. It is therefore recommended that biology teachers in male secondary schools be encouraged to make use of paired-problem-solving strategy so as to boost the academic performance of their students.

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